

Critical Factors Governing Nasal Spray Design And Evaluation

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ABSTRACT

The intranasal route is the preferred method for administering drugs for local, systemic, and central nervous system delivery. A nasal spray is a liquid drug administered into the nasal cavity via a spray device for local or systemic therapeutic effects. Benefits of the nasal spray dosage form, including being cost-effective, convenient to use and carry, and allowing for self-administration, along with high patient adherence, create a growing opportunity for nasal drug delivery. A medicinal molecule can thus be rapidly transported over the singular epithelial cell layer directly into the systemic blood circulation, bypassing first-pass hepatic and intestine digestion. This article emphasizes the important elements of nasal anatomy and physiology along with the biological, physicochemical, and pharmaceutical factors that need to be taken into account during the development of nasal spray formulations. The strategic use of the nasal pathway for the administration of complex pharmaceuticals has garnered significant interest in the pharmaceutical sector in recent years. This review is expected to provide insights into nasal formulation and its in-vitro properties.

Keywords: Nasal Spray, formulation, factors affecting nasal drug delivery, and in-vitro evaluation.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT:

INTRODUCTION

The intranasal method has attracted notable interest in drug research because of its distinct benefits for administering various therapeutics, such as small

molecules, vaccines, hormones, peptides, and proteins. Optimization of nasal drug delivery and subsequent absorption requires a comprehensive assessment of interactions between formulation characteristics, administration parameters, device

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performance, and patient handling. The device and the drug formulation together determine the shape and droplet size of the spray, which in turn affects where the medication lands in the nose. Only in recent years have specially designed devices been developed that can deliver sprays or powders specifically to the olfactory region of the nose, allowing drugs to be administered directly to the central nervous system. The present review summarizes the anatomical, physiological, and histological features of the nasal cavity, along with the major factors influencing nasal drug delivery. It also discusses the drug properties and formulation characteristics that play decisive roles in the pharmacokinetics of nasal preparations. In addition, this article examines nasal spray formulation parameters, excipients, characterization methods, and their impact on key in-vitro tests. [1-2]

Figure 1: Nasal Spray

Delivering drugs intranasally via spray formulations offers a non-invasive alternative with fast therapeutic onset. Their low cost, ease of use and suitability for self-administration lead to strong patient compliance. Therefore, nasal delivery has become an increasingly attractive route with substantial potential for further expansion. A nasal spray is a liquid drug administered into the nasal cavity via a spray device for local or systemic therapeutic effects. Its growing appeal in pharmaceutical research is attributed to multiple main benefits [3-5]:

1. Drug absorption through the intranasal route occurs quickly because of the extensive mucosal surface area and the highly vascularized nature, leading to a rapid onset of action.

2. In contrast to the gastrointestinal tract, the intranasal route prevents drug degradation, maintaining the medication's integrity and efficacy.
3. The intranasal method avoids hepatic first-pass metabolism, which often decreases drug bioavailability via the oral route.
4. Nasal administration is an effective alternative for medications that do not succeed with the oral route.
5. The nasal pathway is efficient for administering small drug molecules, leading to increased bioavailability.
6. The absorption of large molecules can be improved by utilizing absorption enhancers and other methods.
7. This method serves as a substitute for injectable delivery of proteins and peptides.
8. This approach to administration allows for a lower dosage, resulting in fewer side effects.
9. This route provides more convenience for patients needing long-term therapy than parenteral administration.
10. This medication can be directly delivered to systemic circulation and the central nervous system (CNS) by evading the hepatic and blood-brain barrier (BBB).
11. A medication that demonstrates low stability in the gastrointestinal system necessitates a different method of delivery.
12. It is simple to administer and can be self-administered.

Disadvantages:

1. Nasal delivery systems are less convenient for patients compared to oral ones due to the potential for nasal irritation.

2. The nasal cavity provides a less extensive absorptive surface area compared to the gastrointestinal tract.
3. There is inadequate toxicity data concerning penetration enhancement.
4. Nasal disorders might decrease the product's efficacy.
5. A high rate of mucociliary clearance.

ANATOMY AND HISTOLOGY OF HUMAN NASAL CAVITY:

The visible external nose encircles the nostrils of the nasal cavities, complicating the description of one-third of the nasal cavity, which measures 5 cm high and 10 cm in length, comprising a dual structure. The combined surface area of both nasal cavities is around 150 cm², and the total volume is around 15 ml. 1.5 cm

from the nares is the narrowest segment of the airway, known as the internal ostium (or nasal valve), which has a cross-sectional size of approximately 30 mm on each side. The nasal valve constitutes approximately 50% of the overall resistance to respiratory airflow from the nostril to the alveoli. Each nasal cavity is bounded by the septal wall and the lateral wall, characterized by the inferior, middle, and superior turbinates. They are essential for preserving the slit-like cavity, thus enabling the humidification and temperature regulation of inhaled air. Below and lateral to each of the turbinates are channels referred to as the inferior, middle, and superior meatus. The inferior and middle meatus accommodate the orifices of the nasolacrimal duct and the paranasal sinuses. The middle meatus is a significant anatomical region in the pathophysiology of sinus disorders [6].

Figure 2: Anatomy of human nasal cavity [6]

FORMULATION OF NASAL SPRAY [7-8]:

A perfect nasal drug candidate must have these characteristics:

1. Suitable water solubility to deliver the required dosage in a 25–150 ml formulation volume.
2. Suitable nasal absorption characteristics.
3. The medication does not cause nasal irritation.
4. An appropriate clinical justification for nasal dosage forms, such as quick action onset.
5. Minimal dosage. Typically, under 25 mg for each dose.
6. Absence of harmful nasal by-products.
7. No unpleasant smells/scents related to the medication.
8. Appropriate stability features.

Commonly used excipients in nasal spray [7-8]:

Table 1: Commonly used excipients

Sr. No.	Category	Example
1.	Buffer	Sodium phosphate, Sodium citrate, Citric acid
2.	Solubilizer	Glycols, Medium chain glycerides
3.	Preservative	Parabens, phenyl ethyl alcohol, benzalkonium chloride, EDTA and benzoyl alcohol
4.	Antioxidant	Sodium bisulfite, butylated hydroxytoluene, sodium metabisulfite and tocopherol
5.	Humectant	Glycerin, sorbitol and mannitol.
6.	Surfactant	Polysorbate 80, Polysorbate 20
7.	Bioadhesive Polymer	HPMC, Sodium CMC
8.	Penetration Enhancer	Cyclodextrin, Chitosan

Different categories of excipients are utilized in nasal formulations. Frequently utilized and often incorporated excipients include the following [8]

1. Buffers

Nasal fluids might change the pH of the given dose, potentially influencing the availability of un-ionized drug for absorption. Thus, a sufficient formulation buffer capacity might be necessary to sustain the pH in situ. Instances of buffers utilized in nasal spray include sodium phosphate, sodium citrate, and citric acid.

2. Solubilizers

The water solubility of a medication often poses a challenge for delivering drugs nasally in liquid form. Traditional solvents or co-solvents like glycols, minor amounts of alcohol, Transcutol (diethylene glycol monoethyl ether), medium-chain glycerides, and Labrasol (saturated polyglycolized C8-C10 glyceride) may be utilized to improve drug solubility. Additional substances may be employed, for instance, surfactants or cyclodextrins like HP-s Cyclodextrin, which function as biocompatible solubilizers and stabilizers when paired with lipophilic absorption enhancers. In such instances, their effect on nasal irritation must be taken into account.

3. Preservatives

The majority of nasal formulations are water-based, necessitating preservatives to inhibit microbial development. Parabens, phenyl ethyl alcohol,

benzalkonium chloride, EDTA, and benzoyl alcohol are frequently utilized preservatives in nasal products.

4. Antioxidants

A limited amount of antioxidants might be necessary to avoid drug oxidation. Frequently utilized antioxidants include sodium bisulfite, butylated hydroxytoluene, sodium metabisulfite, and tocopherol. Typically, antioxidants have no impact on drug absorption or lead to nasal irritation.

5. Humectants

Allergies and chronic illnesses can lead to crusting and dryness of the mucous membrane. Some preservatives and antioxidants are probably responsible for nasal irritation, particularly when applied in larger amounts. Sufficient moisture in the nasal passages is crucial for avoiding dehydration. Consequently, humectants may be included particularly in gel-formulated nasal products. Humectants prevent nasal irritation and do not influence drug absorption. Typical examples are glycerin, sorbitol, and mannitol.

6. Surfactants

The addition of surfactants to nasal dosage forms can alter the permeability of nasal membranes, potentially enhancing drug absorption through the nasal route. It also enhances the stability of the suspension. Typical instances consist of Polysorbate.

7. Bioadhesive polymers

A bioadhesive polymer is a substance that can engage with biological materials through interfacial forces and remain attached to them for extended durations. They are referred to as mucoadhesive if the biological substance is a mucus membrane. The bioadhesive strength of a polymer material relies on the characteristics of the polymer, the environment (pH), swelling, and physiological elements (mucin

turnover, health condition). For safety (nasal irritancy) reasons, it is often advised to use a mix of carriers.

8. Penetration enhancer

Chemical enhancers for penetration are commonly utilized in nasal drug administration.

FACTORS AFFECTING NASAL DRUG ABSORPTION:

Figure 3: Factors affecting Nasal Spray

Physico-chemical properties of drug ^[9-10]:

Size and weight of molecules

1. The absorption of drugs through the nasal pathway depends on various factors, such as the molecular characteristics of the compound and the size of the particles.
2. Lipophilic drugs demonstrate improved permeability as molecular weight increases, while hydrophilic drugs exhibit diminished permeability with higher molecular weight.

3. Many lipophilic drugs administered intranasally have low molecular weights (<1000 Da), allowing them to cross the mucosal membrane relatively efficiently compared with larger lipophilic compounds. For polar drugs that rely on paracellular transport, molecular weight plays a crucial role in determining both the rate and extent of absorption.
4. The size of the particles is essential: particles greater than 10 μm are likely to settle in the nasal cavity, whereas those smaller than 5 μm are too fine and get inhaled straight into the lungs.

Balance between lipophilicity and hydrophilicity

1. Although it possesses certain hydrophilic traits, the nasal mucosa is mainly lipophilic.
2. This lipophilic characteristic serves as an obstacle, restricting the uptake of hydrophilic medications.
3. Conversely, some lipophilic medications are absorbed nearly entirely, boasting a bioavailability close to 100%, and show a pharmacokinetic profile akin to that of an intravenous injection.

Enzymatic breakdown within the nasal cavity

1. The limited bioavailability seen in the nasal administration of drugs such as proteins and peptides is due to their breakdown in the nasal cavity.
2. A variety of metabolizing enzymes—such as carboxyl esterase, aldehyde dehydrogenases, epoxide hydrolases, glutathione S-transferases, and cytochrome P-450 isoenzymes are found in nasal epithelial cells and alter the drug's pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics.

Polymorphism

1. The polymorphic form of a drug affects its solubility and dissolution rate, making the selection of an appropriate polymorphic form crucial in the development of nasal drug formulations, especially for drugs delivered as particles.

Dissolution rate and solubility

1. Effective intranasal drug delivery depends on the drug's water solubility and its formulation, because it must first dissolve in the nasal fluids—only the dissolved, molecular form can cross the biological membrane.
2. Nevertheless, the limited space of the nasal cavity restricts the volume of liquid that can be given. This presents a difficulty in administering medications with low water

solubility or those needing large doses, which could be harmful to achieve therapeutic effect.

3. Consequently, the ultimate pharmaceutical formulation must be meticulously designed to assure the drug is administered in therapeutically significant amounts.

Nasal mucosal related factors ^[11-14]:

Blood supply and membrane permeability

1. Although the nasal mucosa exhibits high permeability, large molecular weight and water-soluble substances such as proteins and peptides have limited permeability.
2. Parasympathetic activation enhances drug absorption by increasing blood flow and creating congestion, while sympathetic activation limits blood flow and decreases absorption

Mucociliary clearance

1. The nasal cavity employs mucociliary clearance, a natural defence system that relies on ciliary movement, to move dissolved and stuck particles to the nasopharynx for final removal into the gastrointestinal tract.
2. This procedure usually eliminates substances administered nasally in roughly 21 minutes. A reduced clearance rate prolongs the drug's interaction with the nasal mucosa, which boosts permeability, whereas a quicker rate diminishes drug absorption.

Pathological conditions

1. Conditions such as the common cold, different types of rhinitis, and nasal polyposis interfere with mucociliary clearance by modifying nasal secretions and irritating the nasal mucosa, which affects the drug's contact duration with the nasal lining

Nasal secretions

1. Anterior serous and seromucus glands generate nasal secretions at an average rate of 1.5–21 ml per day. The passage of drugs through the nasal mucosa is influenced by three factors:
 2. The viscosity of nasal secretions impacts mucociliary clearance (MCC) by changing the duration of contact between the medication and the mucosa. Excessive viscosity—whether excessively high or low—can hinder the movement of cilia and affect clearance.
 3. Daily fluctuation: Mucociliary clearance decreases during night time because of the body's circadian cycle, affecting the speed and pattern of drug absorption.
 4. pH of nasal secretions: An average pH of 5.5–6.5 in adults and 5.0–7.0 in infants optimizes absorption when a drug mainly exists in its unionized state. This happens when the drug's pKa exceeds the nasal pH. Consequently, the pH of a drug formulation should ideally range from 4.5 to 6.5 and demonstrate strong buffering capacity for improved absorption.
2. This method enhances the uptake of the non-ionized drug forms while preventing mucosal discomfort.
 3. It is crucial to steer clear of a pH lower than 3 or higher than 10, since it has been demonstrated to harm cells and membranes.

Osmolarity

1. An isotonic formulation is favoured since the tonicity of the solution affects the nasal mucosa.

Viscosity

1. A higher viscosity in a medication formulation enhances the drug's interaction time with the mucosa, thereby increasing the likelihood of absorption.
2. Simultaneously, this elevated viscosity hinders normal mucociliary clearance and ciliary movement, thus affecting the drug's permeability.

Volume of solution applied & drug concentration

1. In nasal administration, elements such as drug concentration, dosage, and volume are interconnected and influence efficacy.

Formulation related factors ^[14-16]:

Physical form

1. Although nasal drops are the easiest choice, they present issues with incorrect dosing and quick drainage.
2. Though solution and suspension sprays are favoured over irritating powder & sprays, advanced technologies provide enhanced precision and more enduring results.
3. Recently, innovative systems such as microspheres, liposomes, and films have been created to enhance nasal drug delivery.

pH

1. For optimal drug delivery, the pH of a nasal formulation must align with the natural pH of the nasal mucosa, which ranges from 5.0 to 6.5.

EVALUATION:

Appearance, Color, and Clarity

1. The visual characteristics of the container's contents (i.e., formulation) and the closure system (e.g., pump parts, interior of the container) must match their respective descriptions to indicate the integrity of the drug product.
2. If a color is linked to the formulation (whether initially or from degradation processes during shelf life), the manufacturer should establish a quantitative test with suitable acceptance criteria for the drug product ^[17].

Identification

1. It is suggested that a specific identification test(s) be conducted to confirm the identity of the drug substance within the drug product. Relying solely on chromatographic retention time is insufficient for confirming the identity of the drug substance in the drug product.
2. If the drug consists of a single enantiomer, then at least one method must be specifically adapted to account for that property.

Drug Content (Assay)

1. The analysis of the drug substance in the complete container must be conducted using a procedure that indicates stability.
2. This assessment ensures reliable production (e.g., formulation, filling, sealing). The acceptance criteria (assay limits outlined in official publications) must be strict enough to ensure compliance in other associated attributes (e.g., uniformity of spray content).
3. An appropriate assay method must be developed to evaluate the degradation of the drug substance, its adherence to the container and closure parts, and the possible impact of formulation evaporation and/or leakage.

Impurities and Degradation Products

1. The amounts of degradation products and impurities must be assessed using stability indicating method. Acceptance criteria must be established for both individual and overall degradation products and impurities.
2. Refer to the relevant guidelines for impurity identification and qualification. Any impurity present at or above 0.1% must be identified. Specified impurities and degradation products—whether identified or not—are those individually listed and limited in the drug product specification.

Preservative(s) and Stabilizing Excipient(s) Assay

1. In cases where preservatives, antioxidants, chelating agents, or other stabilizing excipients (such as benzalkonium chloride,

phenylethyl alcohol, edetate) are included in the formulation, a particular assay for these components should be conducted, along with defined acceptance criteria (At a concentration of 0.10 percent or 1.0 milligram daily)^[17-18].

Spray Content Uniformity (SCU)

1. The spray released from the nozzle must be extensively examined for the drug substance concentration of several sprays from a single container, across different containers, and between batches of the drug product.
2. This assessment aims to deliver a comprehensive performance review of a batch, evaluating the formulation, manufacturing procedure, and pump. The quantity of sprays for each determination must not be greater than the quantity of sprays in one dose.
3. A single dose signifies the least number of sprays for each nostril indicated on the product label. To ensure reproducible in vitro dose collection, the method must include controls for actuation parameters (e.g., stroke length, depression force). The test can be conducted with units prepared according to the guidelines in the labelling. The quantity of drug substance administered from the nosepiece should be stated as both the actual quantity and as a percentage of the labelled claim.
4. This test aims to show the consistency of medication per spray (or minimum dose) released from the nosepiece, in accordance with the label claim, for an adequate number (n = 10 is suggested) of containers from a batch.
5. The main objective is to maintain SCU within a single container and across several containers in a batch
6. The subsequent acceptance criteria are suggested:

The quantity of active ingredient for each determination falls within 80–120 percent of the label claim for no more than 1 of 10 containers, none of the determinations exceed 75–125 percent of the label claim, and the average remains within 85–115 percent of the label claim.

In the second tier of batch testing, no more than 3 out of 30 determinations have an active ingredient amount exceeding 80–120 percent of the label claim, all 30 determinations remain within 75–125 percent of the label claim, and the average falls between 85–115 percent of the label claim [18-19].

Spray Content Uniformity (SCU) through container life [17-19]

1. This test aims to evaluate if the product provides the specified number of complete medication sprays that satisfy SCU acceptance standards over the lifespan of the nasal spray unit.
2. The test requires identifying the SCU from the start of unit life and at the labelled claim number of sprays per container for a suitable number of containers (n = 5 is suggested).
3. The subsequent acceptance criteria are suggested.

The level of active ingredient in each determination remains within 80–120 percent of the label claim for no more than 1 out of 10 determinations from five containers, none of the determinations exceeds 75–125 percent of the label claim, and the averages for both the initial and final determinations are within 85–115 percent of the label claim.

pH

1. The pH of the formulation should be evaluated for both solution and suspension nasal sprays, and a suitable acceptance criterion should be defined. In healthy human volunteers, the pH range for the anterior region of the nose was 5.17 to 8.13, whereas the posterior region had a range of 5.20 to 8.00, suggesting that the average baseline nasal pH in humans is roughly 6.3. Therefore,

stability can be attained through the appropriate choice of formulation pH.

2. The pH of the formulation must be close to that of human nasal mucosa (5.0-6.5) to avoid triggering sneezing.

Osmolality

1. For formulations with an agent to regulate tonicity or for products that make a label claim about tonicity, the osmolality of the formulation must be assessed and managed at the time of release. Animal model data indicates that salmon calcitonin from nasal spray formulations with an osmolality of 100 or 600 mOsmol/Kg has higher bioavailability compared to isotonic formulations.
2. Additional research has demonstrated that hypotonic nasal spray formulations enhanced drug permeability across the nasal mucosa. Certain currently available products on the market have indicated osmolality levels between 300 mOsmol/Kg and 700 mOsmol/Kg [19].

Net Content and Weight Loss (Stability)

1. Nasal spray medications must have acceptance standards for net content and weight change during stability testing. As storage orientation is crucial for any weight loss, the drug product needs to be stored in both upright and inverted or upright and horizontal positions to evaluate this attribute.
2. The overall net amount of all formulation ingredients in the complete container must be assessed. The net contents of each of the 10 test containers must comply with the release specification [20].

IN-VITRO BIOEQUIVALENCE TESTS:

1. Single actuation content
2. Priming & Repriming
3. Spray Pattern

4. Plume Geometry
5. Droplet size distribution
6. Drug in small particles or droplets

1. Single actuation content

1. The single-actuation content (SAC) of the nasal spray measures the amount of labelled drug delivered in one spray.
2. SAC for both the Test and Reference products is evaluated using Spray View and monitored from the first to the last actuation to ensure uniform drug delivery, with the content analyzed by HPLC assay.
3. The nasal spray's drug content must be examined for uniformity: inside one container (from the initial to the final spray), between various containers, and across different production batches [21-22].

2. Priming & Repriming

1. Priming in nasal sprays involves performing a specified number of initial actuations to prepare the container so it can accurately deliver the labeled drug amount.
2. Priming must be carried out before the product is used for treatment. The bioequivalence population is assessed after priming, as this step helps prevent inconsistent spray delivery. The required number of primes depends on achieving consistent fine-spray output.
3. Repriming is performed after the product has been stored for a specified duration to confirm accurate delivery of the labeled drug amount. Population bioequivalence (PBE) shall be assessed during repriming [22].

3. Spray pattern

1. The spray pattern test, performed using impaction or non-impaction methods, assesses the geometric characteristics of the emitted spray plume. This evaluation is

conducted at the beginning of the container's life.

2. Testing is performed at two heights ranging from 3 to 7 cm between the nasal spray tip and the laser sheet. Parameters measured include D_{min} , D_{max} , ovality ratio, plume center of gravity, and shot weight, using the SprayView instrument [22-23].

4. Plume Geometry

1. The plume geometry test provides characterization and quantification of the emitted spray plume from a side-view perspective. This assessment is conducted at the initial stage of the product container's life.
2. Using the SprayView instrument, the fully developed plume is captured at a specified time, allowing measurement of plume width, plume angle, and plume height [22-23].

5. Droplet size distribution

1. Droplet-size distribution is determined using laser diffraction, where the Malvern Spraytec device measures the percentage of light scattered by the aerosol plume. This assessment, conducted at both the beginning and end of container life, characterizes the fully developed plume and reports D_{10} , D_{50} , D_{90} , and Span values using three consecutive actuations [22-24].
2. The acceptable droplet-size range for nasal sprays is 30–120 μm . Measurements are taken at two distances from the actuator orifice within 2–7 cm; when measured at 3 cm, the second distance must exceed 3 cm.
3. Comparative evaluation between Test and Reference products is required. Particles with a median size below 10 μm may penetrate the lungs, whereas those above 120 μm may deposit on the nasal mucosa.

6. Drug in small particles or droplets

1. The purpose of this test is to quantify the drug present in fine droplets, thereby determining

the active moiety delivered to the intended site of action. Testing is carried out using an

- Andersen Cascade Impactor (ACI) in compliance with USP <601>, with the flow

rate set at 15 L/min for optimal operation. This evaluation is performed at the beginning of the spray unit's life cycle, using 10 actuations per cycle for analysis [22-24].

Table 2: Marketed Products [25-27]

Drug Substance	Indication	Status	Manufacturer
Diazepam	Seizure	Marketed	Neurelis Inc.
Epinephrine	Type I allergic reactions	Marketed	ARS Pharms Operation
Midazolam	Seizure	Marketed	UCB Inc.
Sumatriptan	Migraine	Marketed	GSK
Zavegepant	Migraine	Marketed	Pfizer
Azelastine Hydrochloride & Fluticasone Propionate	Seasonal allergic rhinitis	Marketed	Mylan Specialty LP
Beclomethasone	Asthma	Marketed	Teva Branded Pharm
Calcitonin salmon	Osteoporosis	Marketed	Apotex Inc.
Esketamine Hydrochloride	Depression	Marketed	Janssen Pharms
Ketorolac	Pain	Marketed	Zyla
Nicotine	Smoking Cessation	Marketed	Pfizer Inc.
Varenicline	Dry eye	Marketed	Oyster Point Pharma
Zolmitriptan	Migraine	Marketed	Pfizer

CONCLUSION:

Given the possible advantages of nasal administration, we can anticipate a variety of innovative nasal products becoming available in the market soon. They will consist of not just medications for localized treatment but also for overall defence against infections. The creation of medications designed to specifically target the brain to achieve effective therapy in the CNS while minimizing systemic side effects. Nasal drug delivery may be influenced by various elements such as Biological Factors, Physiological Factors, Drug Physicochemical Properties, and Formulation Physicochemical Properties. Nasal spray pharmaceutical products consist of active substances dissolved or suspended in solutions or combinations of excipients within non-pressurized dispensers that provide a spray delivering a measured dose of the active substance. The essential evaluation of nasal spray involves examining the spray pattern, droplet size distribution, and spray content uniformity, which depend on both the formulation and the properties of the device.

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